

Exploring Dependence Structure between Oil and Biofuel Commodities: Insights from European and North American Markets

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the interconnectedness between biofuel commodities and oil market. The paper introduces the notion and measures of excess connectedness for networks. It extends previous research by comparing connectedness levels across regions and employs advanced methodologies, including the quantile frequency connectedness technique, which integrates frequency and quantile approaches.

The results show that the interconnectedness of European and North American commodities markets rose during food price crises. Short-term connectedness predominantly drives total connectedness in networks, with stronger dependencies in the tails. Dependencies are generally stronger in the North American market, where oil is pivotal in shock transmission, particularly after 2017.

Keywords: crude oil, biofuels, green transport, connectedness

1 INTRODUCTION

The European Union (EU) and the United States (US), key biofuel producers, are increasingly prioritizing advanced biofuels that do not depend on conventional agricultural commodities as feedstock (OECD and Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, 2019). Nonetheless, first-generation feedstocks, such as maize and sugarcane for ethanol and vegetable oils for biodiesel, are projected to dominate biofuel production over the next decade (OECD and Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, 2023). Over the past years, biofuel production in North America and Europe has risen significantly due to policy measures, including EU directives (The European Parliament and the Council of European Union, 2009, 2018) and the US Renewable Fuels Standard (RFS2) under the Energy Independence and Security Act of 2007 (EISA, 2007) finalized by the Environmental Protection Agency in 2010 (USDA, 2010).

Production patterns differ between these regions. In 2023, the US led global bioethanol production with a 46.4% share, primarily derived from maize, while the EU accounted for 5.3%, using maize, wheat, and sugar beets (OECD and Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, 2023). Canada produced bioethanol using maize and wheat (1.6% of global production). For biodiesel, the EU was the top producer (32.2% of global output), relying on rapeseed oil, palm oil, and waste cooking oils, whereas the US (18.3%) used soybean oil and waste cooking oils. Moreover, Canadian canola oil (North American rapeseed oil variety) is the country's primary biodiesel source (0.7% of global production).

The price of crude oil plays a crucial role in determining the cost of agricultural commodity production, including the biofuel components. This translates into the existence of a relationship between their prices. However, the strength of the dependence between crude oil prices and agricultural commodity prices can vary depending on the specific commodity. It may change over time, which poses a challenge for risk managers who must consider the risk of contagion and transmission of volatility across markets. Although the prices of specific commodities in different parts of the world are closely interconnected—largely due to the increasing globalization of commodity markets, which may, in part, stem from the phenomenon of market financialization (Prokopeczuk et al., 2019; Zhang and Broadstock, 2020; Ouyang and Zhang, 2020; Dudda et al., 2022)—it is possible for the same commodity to exhibit different levels of correlation depending on the region. Therefore, when discussing

the interdependencies between these two markets, it becomes crucial to identify the region where these relationships are stronger and to understand the underlying reasons for these differences.

A significant amount of research explores the connections between energy and agricultural commodity markets. Previous works devoted to the analysis of linkages between the agricultural and oil futures market focused mainly on the more liquid US market (see for example Yang et al. (2025); Ni et al. (2024); Wu et al. (2023); Bouri et al. (2021); Tiwari et al. (2021); Cao and Cheng (2021); Hung (2021); Zhu et al. (2021); Echaust and Just (2020); Ji and Fan (2012)). Similar studies concerning the European market were limited to selected commodities (see: Yahya et al. (2022); Just and Echaust (2022)).

The goal of this paper is to examine the connectedness between biofuel-related commodities (maize, rapeseed, wheat, sugar) and crude oil futures prices in two networks related to both regions. The results of the study expand the conclusions from the previous papers twofold. Firstly, the analysis is extended to account for differences in the connectedness level and compare the results between North American and European markets. In the paper, the excess connectedness measures are defined and calculated for two networks. Secondly, the methods used are multifaceted and go beyond the classic Diebold and Yilmaz (2008, 2012) approach. A connectedness approach was expanded by Baruník and Křehlík (2018) to account for different frequencies or horizons of the investments. Moreover, Ando et al. (2022) and Chatziantoniou et al. (2021) developed a quantile connectedness technique that can be employed to measure spillovers in distinct parts of the variable distribution. In this study, both aspects are thoroughly investigated using the method provided by Chatziantoniou et al. (2022), who integrated both approaches into the quantile frequency connectedness technique.

The paper's results provide evidence of linkages between oil and biofuel-related commodities with the increase in interconnectedness index during the world food price crises: particularly in 2008, in the years 2011-2012, and 2022-2023 after the outbreak of the Russian-Ukrainian war.

The analysis shows that the increase in the total connectedness index in both networks is driven mainly by short-term connectedness. In each analyzed case, there are stronger dependencies in the tails of the distributions than in the average values. The dependencies in the North American market are stronger for all analyzed quantiles. Oil, particularly after the year 2017, plays a more significant role in the transmission of shocks in the American market and is more responsive as well. During the crisis caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, crude oil in the European market was a stronger emitter/receiver of shocks than in the US market.

2 DATA AND METHODS

In the paper, daily closing futures prices of four biofuel-related commodities (maize, sugar, wheat, and rapeseed) and crude oil between January 2004 and February 2024 are analyzed. The data refer to the European and North American markets. The source of the data is the Thomson Reuters Eikon database. Daily log returns are used to construct five-dimensional vectors for which connectedness indices are calculated.

Chatziantoniou et al. (2022) introduced the quantile frequency connectedness approach, which can be viewed as a modification of the previous methods focused on connectedness measures (see, for example, Diebold and Yilmaz (2008), Diebold and Yilmaz (2012), Baruník and Křehlík (2018), Antonakakis et al. (2020), Ando et al. (2022)). A quantile vector autoregression QVAR(p) for a N-dimensional vector \mathbf{x}_t and quantile moving average representation QVMA(∞) is considered:

$$\mathbf{x}_t = \mu(\tau) + \sum_{j=1}^p \Phi_j(\tau) \mathbf{x}_{t-j} + \mathbf{u}_t(\tau) = \mu(\tau) + \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \Psi_i(\tau) \mathbf{u}_{t-i}(\tau), \quad (1)$$

where τ is a quantile level and p is a lag length of QVAR model. The H-step ahead quantile generalized forecast error variance decomposition is applied to measure the impact of a shock in series j on series i regarding its forecast error variance share and to calculate the normalized version of this value:

$$\theta_{ij}(H) = \frac{\frac{1}{(\Sigma(\tau))_{jj}} \sum_{h=0}^H \left((\Psi_h(\tau) \Sigma(\tau))_{ij} \right)^2}{\sum_{h=0}^H (\Psi_h(\tau) \Sigma(\tau) \Psi_h'(\tau))_{ii}}, \quad (2)$$

$$\tilde{\theta}_{ij}(H) = \frac{\theta_{ij}(H)}{\sum_{j=1}^N \theta_{ij}(H)}. \quad (3)$$

One can calculate the total directional connectedness transmitted by series i TO others:

$$TO_i(H) = \frac{\sum_{i=1, i \neq j}^N \tilde{\theta}_{ji}(H)}{N}, \quad (4)$$

and FROM other series received by series i :

$$FROM_i(H) = \frac{\sum_{i=1, i \neq j}^N \tilde{\theta}_{ij}(H)}{N}. \quad (5)$$

Eventually, in the time domain the total connectedness index (TCI) measures the average degree of network interconnectedness and equals:

$$TCI(H) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N TO_i(H)}{N} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N FROM_i(H)}{N}. \quad (6)$$

In the frequency domain, TCI is defined according to the Baruník and Křehlík (2018) technique and equals the sum of the corresponding frequency connectedness measures calculated for a specific frequency ranges d :

$$TCI = \sum_d TCI(d), \quad (7)$$

where

$$TCI(d) = \frac{\sum_{i=1, i \neq j}^N \tilde{\theta}_{ij}(d)}{N}. \quad (8)$$

In this paper, two frequency bands related to the short-term and long-term part of dynamics (from 1 to 5 days and from 6 to infinite days) are considered: $d_1 = (\frac{\pi}{5}, \pi)$ and $d_2 = (0, \frac{\pi}{5}]$. If $d = (a, b)$, then $\tilde{\theta}_{ji}(d) = \int_a^b \tilde{\theta}_{ij}(\omega) d\omega$, where

$$\theta_{ij}(\omega) = \frac{\frac{1}{\sum_{jj}} |\sum_{h=0}^{\infty} (\Psi(e^{-i\omega h}) \Sigma)_{ij}|^2}{\sum_{h=0}^{\infty} (\Psi(e^{-i\omega h}) \Sigma \Psi(e^{-i\omega h}))_{ii}}, \quad (9)$$

$$\tilde{\theta}_{ij}(\omega) = \frac{\theta_{ij}(\omega)}{\sum_{j=1}^N \theta_{ij}(\omega)}. \quad (10)$$

The indicated measures refer to the vector \mathbf{x}_t associated with the network X. If analogous values are determined for vector \mathbf{y}_t (for network Y), it is possible to compare the strength of the connectedness, and one can consider comparative connectedness measures for two networks. The excess total connectedness index of network X compared to network Y measures the superiority of TCI of network X compared to network Y and is defined as:

$$TCI_EXCESS^{XY}(H) = TCI^X(H) - TCI^Y(H). \quad (11)$$

A positive sign of the index indicates that the interconnectedness of network X is stronger than that of network Y and reveals a greater integration of X.

The excess directional connectedness TO others measures how much of a shock in series i is transmitted TO all other series j in network X compared to network Y:

$$TO_i_EXCESS^{XY}(H) = TO_i^X(H) - TO_i^Y(H). \quad (12)$$

A positive sign of the index indicates that the variable i plays a more significant role in the transmission of shocks in market X, and is more influential than in market Y.

The excess directional connectedness FROM others measures how much of a series i is receiving FROM all other series j in network X compared to network Y:

$$FROM_i_EXCESS^{XY}(H) = FROM_i^X(H) - FROM_i^Y(H). \quad (13)$$

A positive sign of the index indicates that the variable i is subject to stronger shocks originating from other variables in market X and therefore is more responsive than in market Y.

3 RESULTS

Figures 1 - 8 present the estimation results¹. The figures 1 - 4 focus on the time-dependent short- and long-term interconnectedness of the markets, conditioned on the quantile analyzed. The analysis of connectedness across different frequencies offers a more detailed examination than the time-domain connectedness approach, since market participants operate on different investment horizons Baruník and Křehlík (2018). Incorporating quantiles provides additional insight into tail dependencies, hence it shows whether a network is connected in periods of declines related to crises or increases resulting from stock market optimism. The findings reveal an increase in the interconnectedness index during the world food price crises: in 2008 (coinciding with the global financial crisis of 2008/2009), the world food price crisis of 2011-2012, and in the aftermath of the Russo-Ukrainian war in the years 2022-2023.

In both networks, short-term connectedness is dominant, with stronger dependencies observed in the tails compared to the center of the distribution. These specific effects are stable over time and are consistent with the results of previous studies (see for example the results of Baruník and Křehlík (2018) and Chatziantoniou et al. (2022)). Particularly intensive dependencies in the tails of the distribution can be found in the years 2008, 2011-2012, when strong price changes occurred in the agricultural commodity markets.

Moreover, the level of connectedness is compared between North America and Europe using excess measures presented in the figures 5 - 8. The goal of the comparison is to determine whether a specific network is stronger and more integrated on average. It is possible that certain levels of dependence co-occur, which may be due to common factors affecting both markets, such as the global macroeconomic situation or the bull/bear market on financial markets.

The estimation results show that interconnectedness in the North American market is more pronounced across all quantiles analyzed (see: figures 5 and 6). The predominance of American market connectedness occurs in the case of dependencies for both short- and long-term horizons. This shows that the agricultural commodity market for biofuels and conventional fuels is more integrated in North America than in Europe. As a result, shocks are transmitted within the network with greater intensity, presenting a challenge to risk managers of multi-commodity investment portfolios.

Figure 7 shows that crude oil plays a greater role in the transmission of shocks TO other commodities in the American market, particularly after 2017. A similar conclusion can be formulated based on the values of directional connectedness FROM oil to others (see: figure 8). Hence, American oil is more closely connected with other commodities than the European benchmark. However, during the COVID-19 pandemic, crude oil in the European market emerged as a stronger emitter and receiver of shocks than in the U.S. market. Clearly, during this period, WTI oil prices were strongly affected by the market forces, which did not affect other elements of the American commodities network.

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

First-generation feedstocks, such as maize and sugarcane for ethanol and vegetable oils for biodiesel, are still an important part of the biofuels market. The price of crude oil plays a significant role in the production costs of agricultural commodities, including biofuel components, leading to a relationship between their prices. The globalized nature of commodity markets results in specific price correlations for the commodities. The strength of this relationship varies depending on the specific commodity and region, posing challenges for risk managers in addressing the transmission of shocks between markets.

¹Estimation is done using the R software program and the package ConnectednessApproach by Gabauer (2022)

Figure 1. Short-term dynamic connectedness index in North-American market over time and quantiles

Notes: Results are based on a QVAR model with a 200 days rolling-window size, a lag length of order one, and a 100-step-ahead generalized forecast error variance decomposition.

Figure 2. Short-term dynamic connectedness index in European market over time and quantiles

Figure 3. Long-term dynamic connectedness index in North-American market over time and quantiles

Figure 4. Long-term dynamic connectedness index in European market over time and quantiles

Figure 5. Excess dynamic short-term connectedness index of American market compared to European market over time and quantiles

Figure 6. Excess dynamic long-term connectedness index of American market compared to European market over time and quantiles

Figure 7. The excess directional connectedness of oil TO others: American market compared to European market over time and quantiles

Figure 8. The excess directional connectedness of oil FROM others: American market compared to European market over time and quantiles

The paper presents the concept and metrics of excess connectedness for two networks. The connectedness between crude oil prices and biofuel-related commodities (maize, rapeseed, wheat, sugar) in two networks representing North American and European markets is analyzed. The analysis accounts for regional differences in connectedness and employs advanced methodologies, including the quantile and frequency connectedness techniques.

The findings reveal an increase in the interconnectedness indices during crisis periods, such as the world food price crisis coinciding with the global financial crisis of 2008/2009, the world food price crisis of 2011-2012, and significant food price inflation in the years 2022-2023. In both networks, short-term connectedness is dominant, with stronger dependencies observed in the tails of the distributions compared to average values. Interconnectedness in the North American market is more pronounced across all quantiles analyzed, with crude oil playing a greater role in shocks' transmission across the network, particularly after 2017. The paper's results show that the North American commodities market is more integrated and subject to stronger shock flows. However, during the COVID-19 pandemic, crude oil in the European market emerged as a stronger emitter and receiver of shocks than in the North American market.

The research has some limitations. First, as in each study that utilizes data on the agricultural market one could extend the set of variables. The study uses a limited number of commodities used in biofuel production to enable a consistent comparison between the North American and European markets. Secondly, one could also analyze other aspects of networks' features, such as connectedness related to volatility or liquidity of the market, which could be an interesting topic for further research.

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6 DECLARATION OF GENERATIVE AI AND AI-ASSISTED TECHNOLOGIES IN THE WRITING PROCESS

During the preparation of this work, the author used the free version of Grammarly to correct the grammar of the article. After using this tool, the author reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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